

GDPR in Research– CHEAT SHEET

Personal Data

GENERAL

Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person.

Any information = including research data, metadata and administrative data.

Identified = directly relatable to a person.

Identifiable = traceable to a person.

Natural person = living people, no organisations.

SPECIAL CATEGORIES OF PERSONAL DATA

Take extra care for data about

- racial or ethnic origin
- political opinions
- religious or philosophical beliefs
- trade union membership
- genetic data
- biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person
- health
- a person's sex life or sexual orientation

Planning

GOAL SETTING

Consider and document what personal data you are collecting, the legal basis (often informed consent) and how long you are going to store it.

DATA MINIMISATION

Do not (plan to) collect more personal data than necessary for your research.

LIABILITY

Make sure you know who is responsible and liable for the management of personal data in your research.

ETHICS AND INFORMED CONSENT

Ask your institute's ethics committee if you need ethical approval for your research.

Follow proper informed consent procedures.

TRANSPARENCY

Arrange what personal data is collected, with what purpose, who has access to it and how it will be stored, processed, archived, and (possibly) published.

AND inform all involved parties of these arrangements (including participants).

RDM POLICY

Check your institute's RDM policy for resources, workflow, tools, etc. relevant to working with personal data.

(Pre)DPIA

Fill out a pre-DPIA (Data Protection Impact Assessment).

During research

MINIMISATION OF USE

The fewer people who have access, the better. Make clear arrangements in case you need to share personal data during research. Decide on the rights of the collaborators towards the data (read only or editing).

(PSEUD/AN)ONYMISATION

Anonymise or pseudonymise to the extent possible to still allow you and -if applicable- data (re)users to answer the research question(s).

SECURITY MEASURES

Make sure your storage location and used tools are suitable for personal data.

RIGHTS OF DATA SUBJECTS

Make sure that you can comply with participants' rights. Most importantly, their 'right to be informed' and 'right to be forgotten'.

DATA QUALITY

Make sure your data is accurate, complete and up-to-date.

After research

ARCHIVING & PUBLISHING

Choose a trustworthy and FAIR enabling repository to preserve or archive your data for the long term and in compliance with your informed consent.

PUBLISHING

Make sure that you do not share any (personal) information that you are not allowed to share under the selected access level.

Select an appropriate licence or Data Use Agreement to complement your data.

Useful sites

GDPR

<https://gdpr.eu>

DATA BREACH

Report data breaches at Radboud University's ICT department
+31 24 362 22 22

Contact

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

Data stewards:

www.ru.nl/datastewards

Digital Competence Centre

dcc@ru.nl

PRIVACY

Privacy officers:

<https://www.ru.nl/en/contact/privacy-officers>